

B

Association (source node-target node)	Edge	Source node	Target node
Protein-Pathway	68,856	7,298	1,974
Protein-Functional Domain	1,711,017	990,504	7,834
Protein-PTM	872	308	677
Protein-Molecular Function	743,539	166,338	4,528
Protein-Biological Process	2,621,261	188,237	17,670
Protein-Cellular Component	466,057	124,988	2,152
Protein-Protein Interaction	64,517	11,091	44,819
Protein-Disease	27,282	6,806	5,234
Chemical-Protein	436,831	9,426	14,397
Chemical-Disease	74,757	5,251	1,731
Chemical-Molecular Function	3,274	1,154	229
Chemical-Biological Process	60,974	5,357	3,976
Chemical-Cellular Component	136	92	54
Total	6,279,374	1,020,716	98,720

2 Figure 1) **Overview of the KG** A) A graphical representation of all databases utilized in the
3 construction of the KG with the node type label listed inside the representation of each
4 corresponding database. B) Abundance of associations with corresponding edge and node counts
5 that exist in the KG. C) Visual representation of the node types present within the KG generated
6 from the listed databases above. The circles represent nodes (entities), and the lines represent
7 edges (relationships). The circles are colored according to node type. The labels inside the circle
8 are specific examples of data found in our KG related to the dark kinase CDK13. The labels
9 outside of the circles correspond to the node type in bold text and the edge type in italics.

10
 11 **Figure 2) RegPattern2Vec Overview.** A) The meta-paths produced through our modified
 12 random walk approach are turned into embeddings for representation learning. Once the node
 13 context has been vectorized we then use logistic regression to perform link prediction as a binary
 14 classification task. B) A hypothetical subgraph of the KG. The dashed lines show the node
 15 sequences highlighted in panel D. Nodes are labeled and colored according to node types as
 16 shown in panel C with numbering corresponding to the order in which it is sampled (IE: *P3* is the
 17 third *Protein* node sampled). This figure serves as a graphical depiction of how various data

18 types exist within a neighborhood for sampling. C) The regular pattern designed for random
19 walk sampling (schema). This pattern is defined as *Protein* [*^Pathway*] + *Protein Pathway*. Each
20 random walk instance is constrained based on this pattern. D) The hypothetical sequence of
21 nodes produced by random walks guided by the regular pattern, shown in panel C. All meta-
22 paths must start with either a *DarkKinase* or *Protein* node and must end with a protein and then
23 pathway node (as depicted in panel C).

24

25 Figure 3) **PCA of Vector Embeddings** of all nodes generated by Machine Learning model.

26 Given that the defined schema of RegPattern2Vec is defined as *Protein* [*^Pathway*] + *Protein*

27 *Pathway* when clustering the vector embeddings, we considered all nodes to be of type: *Protein*,

28 anything that is not a *Pathway-Protein* (others), and *Pathways*.

ROC Curve

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30 Figure 4) **Comparing AUC ROC Curves** of RegPattern2Vec and differing schemas utilized
31 with the metapath2vec model. AUC ROC curves were generated by excluding 50% of the known
32 associations from the training set, link prediction was then carried out using a logistic regression
33 algorithm type as the binary classification model. metapath 1 consists of the schema [*Protein*,
34 *FunctionalDomain*, *Protein*, *Pathway*, *Protein*]. metapath 2 consists of the schema [*Protein*,
35 *DarkKinase*, *Protein*, *Pathway*, *Protein*]. metapath 3 consists of the schema [*LightKinase*,
36 *Protein*, *DarkKinase*, *Protein*, *Pathway*, *LightKinase*]. metapath 1 was the best performing
37 schema tested, metapath 2 was still among our top performing schemas tested, and metapath 3
38 was among the worst performing schemas tested.

40 **Figure 5) Investigating the Overlap Among All Replicates and NW Hyperparameter Values**
41 A) Total number of overlapping dark kinase-pathway predictions for all variations of the NW
42 hyperparameter tested (10-80) with replicates (each hyperparameter tested three times) for a total
43 of 24 datasets compared. Replicates were averaged and then graphed. Finally, overlap between
44 all 24 datasets was compared in the “All Overlap” bar B) Graph depicting the number of
45 overlapping pathways for the top ten (out of 95) kinases ranked by number (abundance) of
46 overlapping predictions C) We highlight a portion of the subgraph for the nodes collected
47 through our modified random walk process for the protein-pathway prediction generated through
48 link prediction between *PRKACB* and *DAG/IP3* signaling. The nodes shown are common
49 between five paths in the KG, obtained through the variation in NW datasets described above.
50 *PRKACB* was chosen for this analysis based on panel B. The key indicates the color-coded node
51 types, and the magnified panel highlights the highly connected hubs and their edge types.

52

53 Figure 6) **Investigating the Protein-Pathway Predictions with IDG Experimentally**

54 **Validated Predictions.** Protein Interaction and Proximity (PPI) data for dark kinases obtained

55 through the Dark Kinase Knowledgebase were used as input for Reactome. These predictions
56 were then compared to those produced by our model using data produced during the
57 hyperparameters exercise (24 datasets). A) Graph depicting the number of overlapping pathways
58 between the two datasets for the top ten kinases ranked by number (abundance) of overlapping
59 predictions. B) We highlight a portion of the subgraph for the nodes collected through our
60 modified random walk process for the protein-pathway prediction generated through link
61 prediction between *CDK19* and *TGF-beta*. The nodes shown are common between five paths in
62 the KG, obtained through the 40 NW dataset described above. *CDK19* was chosen for this
63 analysis based on panel A. The key indicates the color-coded node types, and the magnified
64 panel highlights the highly connected hubs and their edge types.

65

66 Figure 7) A Subgraph of the Network Context of the KG Surrounding PSKH2. As
 67 demonstrated in the previous Fig. 5B our model can generate consistent predictions for dark
 68 kinase PSKH2. We compared the predictions produced by our model (40 NW) and Reactome
 69 enrichment using unpublished mass-spectrometry data produced by our collaborators. We
 70 highlight a portion of the subgraph for the nodes collected through our modified random walk
 71 process for the protein-pathway prediction generated through link prediction between *PSKH2*
 72 and *Cilium Assembly*. The nodes shown are common between five paths in the KG, obtained
 73 through the 40 NW dataset. The key indicates the color-coded node types, and the magnified
 74 panel highlights the highly connected hubs and their edge types.